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An Automatic Assessment System for CAD Education

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ABSTRACT

Computer aided design (CAD) is widely used in mechanical engineering to create models of part geometry. Current CAD education at Aalto University relies heavily on course assistants assessing exercises manually. This paper presents a novel system for automatically assessing mechanical engineering parametric CAD modelling exercises. A review of different possibilities for automatic assessment was conducted and a prototype online automatic assessment system for parametric 3D CAD modelling exercises was developed. The system used an interface found in a commercial CAD tool to compare submitted modelling exercises to correct reference models or known values. The system was tested with 102 students on a course and a user experience survey was conducted. Results of the survey indicate that students generally approve of the possibility to use an online service to submit exercises independent of time and place and to get immediate feedback. Automatic assessment systems also reduce the

amount of human work required. Future plans at Aalto University include extending existing e-learning platforms with newly developed automatic assessment tools to create MOOC-style basic CAD courses.

1 INTRODUCTION

In mechanical engineering, computer aided design (CAD) tools are used to create 3-dimensional models of parts. In parametric CAD tools, the model geometry is created with features, which can have references to other features or model geometry. Designing efficient models in requires both technical skills with the tools and strategic skills to structure the model so that it is versatile and can be re-used. The aim of CAD education is to teach both of these skills [1].

At Aalto University, all mechanical engineering students take a basic course in CAD. The assessment of the course exercises has relied on manual assessment by the course assistants, which poses a significant amount of work for a large course. Consistent grading of CAD exercises is challenging, since small errors can lead to large differences in the end result. An automatic online assessment system for CAD exercises could aid in solving these problems.

Automatic exercise assessment systems have been used in other fields, such as the education of computer programming. Literature on automatic assessment systems reveals several benefits of using such systems. An online automatic assessment system reduces manual work by course instructors and ensures grading each submission in a consistent manner [2]. In addition, benefits of an online system include having the system always available, which gives students the possibility to progress on the exercises at any pace. Another benefit of using automatic exercise assessment tools is that students receive immediate feedback after submitting an exercise, which enables learning from failures [2].

The authors of the paper are not aware of previous automatic assessment systems for parametric CAD exercises. A possible explanation for such systems not existing is that CAD software packages are commonly commercial and closed source; programs from different manufacturers also have differing tools and differing ways to access them programmatically. The aim of this research was to create and test an assessment system for parametric CAD modelling exercises.

The current study presents a novel system to assess parametric 3D CAD exercises automatically by using software to extract information from models with tools already found in a commercial CAD software package. The paper also presents evaluation of experiences and survey results of using the system on a basic technical university CAD course.

2 FEATURE BASED PARAMETRIC CAD IN MECHANICAL ENGINEERING

In mechanical engineering, feature based parametric CAD programs are used to design parts and assemblies. These modern 3D CAD systems can describe objects with solid models, which use a combination of surfaces and boundaries to define the volume inside and outside an object [3]. In feature based CAD systems, the part

models consist of feature trees and the features can have references to parameters, other features or geometry, such as edges or surfaces. When a feature or a parameter is changed, the change is reflected to the geometry down the feature tree. [4] An example of a parametric model is presented in figure 1.

Fig. 1. A parametric CAD model of a Lego block and its feature tree. Three parameters control the shape of the block: width (SIZE V), length (SIZE H) and if its thickness (THIN).

Parameters are non-geometric features in a CAD-model [5]. Defining a CAD model with parameters, constraints and features improves efficiency by enabling the re-use and reshape models [5]. Relating model features to parameters enables regenerating the part in different shapes. A good practice is to construct the model around a parametric skeleton, which contains centralized design information and conveys *design intent* about the part [5]. For example, when altering a skeleton model, the more detailed geometry in a model follows changes in major dimensions.

Commercial CAD software packages contain application programming interfaces (API) which can be used to drive the software programmatically without user interaction in the graphical user interface. In industry, the APIs are used for model automation, but they can also be used to drive tools necessary for the automatic assessment of exercises. [4]

CAD education Successful and productive 3D CAD requires declarative (3-dimensional perception, technical competence with the tools) and strategic skills (building and structuring the whole model) [1]. On basic courses the objective is to give a fundamental understanding of how the software and tools work and how geometry is created [4]. The aim of more advanced CAD courses is to teach both declarative and strategic skills. Advanced CAD education can focus on upper-level concepts, such as conveying design intent in the structure of the CAD model, by parametrizing the most important features of a model [4].

A typical master’s degree in mechanical engineering in a Finnish university includes from 5 to 10 ECTS credits of CAD courses. Most CAD courses in Finnish universities consist of using commercial CAD tools to complete different types of 3D modelling and

2D drawing exercises. The courses typically rely on course assistants checking and assessing the work of students. University curricula are not limited to CAD education only; collaborative tools and simulation tools are often taught together with CAD. [4]

3 AUTOMATIC ASSESSMENT OF EXERCISES

Automatic assessment tools

In software engineering, automatic tests are used to discover faults in programs and to inspect whether programs meet specified requirements [6]. Assessing any other exercises addresses the same problem; the assessment method must inspect whether the returned exercise has faults and measure how well the returned exercise meets a given set of conditions. In the education of computer programming, automatic exercise assessment tools have established a foothold and many educational institutions have successfully used automated assessment systems. [7]

The use of automatic exercise assessment in programming education is based on practices used in software testing, where industrial testing frameworks exist to test the functionality of written code. Some systems used for programming exercise assessment work by applying tools found in testing frameworks on the submitted code. Other possible approaches include comparing input and output of the code or comparing graphs of the submitted solutions to known correct answers. [8]

Using automatic assessment effectively requires considering the limitations of the automatic assessment method when designing the exercises [7]. For example, assessment tasks easy for a human mind may not be easy for software-based assessment systems. Limiting the number of submissions can be used as a tool to prevent trial and error type solutions [8]. It is also possible to parametrize the exercises to generate varying exercise instances separately for each student and resubmission [8].

E-learning systems as user interfaces for automatic assessment tools

E-learning systems can be categorized into automatic assessment systems and learning management systems, of which the latter are used to manage courses and assignments [9]. A review of automatic assessment systems [9] shows that it has been common for learning systems to have been implemented for a very specific use case and to have incorporated features from both system types. Furthermore, previous studies suggest that this fragmentation was due to the tools having been developed in separate thesis projects and by individual teachers to support specific teaching requirements on their courses [8].

Recently e-learning environments have been developed, which separate different distinct features into modules communicating between each other via documented interfaces [9]. For example, the A-plus system at Aalto university separates different layers of the systems: the user interface and authentication is handled separately and there are external synchronous, asynchronous or static methods available for the assessment [4][9].

4 AUTOMATIC ASSESSMENT SYSTEM FOR PARAMETRIC CAD EXERCISES

The research aimed at developing an automatic assessment system and to test it on a basic CAD course at Aalto University. The course *computer aided tools in engineering sciences* is common for all mechanical engineering bachelor students in Aalto University School of Engineering. The course consists of modules where students learn to use different CAD programs for a typical set of tasks.

The system was developed for the course's Creo Parametric module. Creo Parametric is a 3D CAD software developed by PTC. The software includes tools for solid and surface modeling of parts, sheet metal and weld modeling and technical documentation [10].

4.1 Assessing CAD exercises automatically

All exercise assessment is essentially measuring how well the solution of the exercise meets a given set of requirements and then grading the submission based on predefined a set of criteria. There are several approaches to automatically assessing exercises, but for all cases it is necessary to specify the requirements for assessment and criteria for grading. The concepts presented in this section can be applied to automatic assessment of any CAD exercises, but the implemented system is specific for Creo Parametric.

To automatically assess CAD exercises, it is possible to use APIs in CAD software packages to compare data from the submitted CAD files to known values or data from another file. The APIs can be used to programmatically regenerate the model with different parameter sets and then check if it matches to a reference model. The APIs also provide access to other sources of information (such as the volume, surface area and center of gravity) that can be used to check if a model is correctly constructed.

Proxies for the correctness of geometry include the feature tree and mass properties of a model. Comparing only the feature trees is not always enough, because the same geometry can be constructed with different features; having correct geometry does not necessarily mean having a matching feature tree. The mass properties of a model contain information of the total volume, mass, surface area and centers of gravity of the model, which can be compared with the respective information from a correct model. Commercial CAD software packages also have tools which can be used to compare and visualize differences the geometries of two models (figure 2).

Fig. 2. The *Compare geometry* tool in Creo Parametric 3.0 can be used to visualize differences in two models. A similar tool exists in Solidworks [4].

Several standard exchange formats exist to transfer 3D geometry information between CAD systems of different manufacturers. Examples of these neutral file formats are STEP and IGES. Parametric features are not supported in these formats and they do not store information of the history of the part in the same way as proprietary file formats [3][4]. A manufacturer-independent CAD exercise assessment system could make use of neutral file formats, but the assessment would be limited to geometry only.

4.2 CADVER: Automatic exercise assessment system for Creo Parametric

After a review of available options for automatic assessment of parametric CAD models, the prototype system CADVER was developed.¹ The system had an online interface, through which students could submit the exercise and view the assessment results.

The system uses the VBAPI available in Creo 3.0 and can be used to regenerate models with different parameter sets (example of a parameter set for the Lego block exercise in figure 3). When the part has been regenerated, the system uses the API functions to compare information from the model to predefined values or a known correct model. The system supports comparing mass properties (e.g. volume and mass), feature trees, and checking if the model successfully regenerates with given parameters.

When a file is submitted to the system, the system runs the appropriate check tasks based on check templates configured in the system. Checks were implemented for matching surface area or volume of the models to given given values or values read from a reference file. A check was also available to check for a matching of feature types present in the model's feature tree. An admin panel for the system was also implemented to display information of passed and failed check tasks user by user.

¹ The developed automatic assessment system (CADVER) is open source and available at <https://github.com/tuomastiainen/cadver>

```
[{"SIZE_V": 1, "SIZE_H": 5, "THIN": true},
{"SIZE_V": 2, "SIZE_H": 1, "THIN": false},
{"SIZE_V": 1, "SIZE_H": 2, "THIN": false},
{"SIZE_V": 3, "SIZE_H": 5, "THIN": false}]
```

1 2 3 4

Fig. 3. Example of a parameter set used to test the parametric Lego block exercise. The system regenerates the model with all parameter combinations in the set and compares the result to a reference. The reference can be another model or predefined values.

Automating the use *compare geometry* tools for assessment proved to be difficult, and the implemented system did not utilize these tools. The tools can directly produce visual feedback, which would be useful because the feedback can convey information of how the part is incorrect, not just that it is incorrect.

4.3 Evaluating the performance of the developed system

The developed system was evaluated in two ways:

- The CADVER system was tested on a basic CAD course at Aalto University and a survey was conducted. The survey was originally conducted as a part of a master's thesis [4]. Students were required to submit the Lego exercise (figure 1) modelled on Creo Parametric 3.0 to the automatic system and answer to a survey assessing the background of the students, user experience and the learning experience with the automatic system.
- A collection of exercises from was run through the automatic assessment system to check if they pass or fail the assessment
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5 RESULTS

The system was successfully deployed and tested, both manually and online on a university basic CAD course. Analysis and visualizations of the conducted survey results are presented. The results indicate that students generally approved of the system.

102 students returned the exercise (95 accepted, 7 failed) and 91 answered the survey. The scale in figures 4–9 is the number of answers, the options for the survey questions are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Options for the survey questions

1	Disagree
2	Somewhat disagree
3	Neither agree nor disagree
4	Somewhat agree
5	Agree

Overall, the results of the survey were similar to results from previous studies concerning e-learning and automatic assessment. The main result was that the possibility to submit exercise independent of time and place is viewed positively among the students. Most students generally approved of the exercise instructions and the instructions on how to submit them to the automatic assessment system.

The results suggest that students felt that the system supported their learning (figure 8) Most students answered that they prefer using automatic assessment systems compared to submitting the work to course staff 9. Majority of the students also trusted that the system assessed their work correctly (figure 6). Most students did not see the feedback of the system as sufficient (figure 5). For each submission, the system only displayed the checks applied to the exercise with their results; the system could benefit from more visual feedback.

Almost half of the students completed and submitted the exercises without assistance from course staff (figure 7). The reasons for this might be that the students already had some experience with parametric CAD modelling. The exercise was not the first exercise on the course, and due to rearrangements made in Aalto University courses, over a third of the students had completed the exercise before. 40% of the students had previously used automatic exercise assessment systems.

Fig. 4. The automatic assessment system supported my learning.

Fig. 5. The feedback provided by the automatic assessment system is sufficient.

Fig. 6. I trust that the automatic assessment system assessed my work correctly.

Fig. 7. I needed assistance from course staff to complete the exercise.

Fig. 8. The automatic assessment system supported my learning.

Fig. 9. I prefer using automatic assessment systems compared to submitting the work to course staff.

The system was also tested on an archive of old exercise submissions by students on courses in the past. It successfully identified several incorrectly constructed models, where a certain parameter sets produced a faulty output. This is probably because human assessment had failed to catch certain edge cases; for a human it is not possible to check a high number of parameter combinations in a reasonable time.

In some studies, the amount of false positives (exercises which are not correct but are reported correct by the system) in automatic assessment has been investigated. In this study, the amount of false positives was not evaluated, but the majority of students were confident that the system assessed their exercises correctly. When using automatic assessment systems, which compare input and output, it is important that the exercise and task are unambiguous and that the assessment is not dependent on how the output was achieved.

6 DISCUSSION

Students generally give positive feedback about online automatic assessment systems on courses. Especially students value the possibility to make progress on courses independently of time and place. The generally positive feedback received from students in the survey was along the lines of previous research.

Based on these results, further conclusions cannot be made about how the utilization of automatic assessment systems actually affect learning. It is possible, that automatic assessment does not have positive effects on learning. Completing exercises independently without interaction between a course assistant reduces feedback and in class, students get an understanding of their own skills, when they get to see the work of others. A potential positive effect is that more students in total might take courses which do not require attendance. The amount of required human resources per student is also significantly lower on courses with automatic assessment.

For the assessment of many exercises an approach where only inputs and outputs are compared can be sufficient. Similar methods that have already been in use in programming and mathematical education can be applied to exercise types specific to mechanical engineering, such as 3D parametric CAD modelling. More complicated exercises which include the evaluation of actual design choices will require human

assessment in the foreseeable future. When using automatic assessment, the suitability of the exercises for automatic assessment must be taken into account in the design phase of the course.

Many other types of exercises in the domain of mechanical engineering would be suitable for implementing automatic assessment using simple methods, such as comparing the output of a simulation model to a known output of a correct model with the same input. The use of automatic assessment in the education of mechanical engineering can be further expanded and new automatic assessment tools will be needed to assess new types of exercises.

Since automatic assessment tools have been used in other fields, and service-oriented systems already exist, duplicate work could be avoided if new assessment systems are integrated directly into existing e-learning systems.

During the last few years, several universities have opened Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC). The courses are typically free of charge, the materials are available online, students can progress on the course at their own pace and the exercises may be assessed automatically. The development of automatic assessment tools opens possibilities to create MOOC courses for new domains, such as mechanical engineering. MOOC courses have received criticism from the pedagogical viewpoint. MOOC courses should be used as tools to create a higher learning impact with the available resources, not as tools to minimize the effort put into teaching.

To conclude, in this research a novel system to assess mechanical engineering parametric CAD exercises was developed and successfully tested. Work continues at Aalto University to extend the functionalities of such systems and to establish MOOC style introductory level courses for mechanical engineering.

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